

COMPLEX PSYCHOLOGICAL AND ART SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF PRINTED TEXTS WITH EROTIC AND PORNOGRAPHIC CONTENT

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the comprehensive psycho-artistic examination of printed texts with erotic and pornographic content. During the article, the authority of each expert participating in the expertise process is explained, and the questions to be put before them are recommended.*

Keywords: *court, expert-psychologist, expert-sexologist, art, pornography, erotica.*

It is known that photos showing naked genitals, often in a depraved state, sexual life or sexual depravity make the viewer psychologically erotic-sexually excited and affect his imagination.

Photos in the sense of eroticism involuntarily direct the human imagination to the sphere of sex, that is, they stimulate the sexual orientation of the imagination. Artificially generated arousal does not always end in normal sexual satisfaction. As a rule, in such cases, under the influence of artificially created arousal, the forms of satisfaction of sexual desire are also artificial. Thus, the manifestation of sexual activity in a distorted form increases.

Pornographic products are naturalistic, lewd depictions of sexual acts on the themes of pedophilia, zoophilia, sadomasochism, and necrophilia. Perversions, all other types of deviations from the norm are not currently considered pornography by many authors.

We believe that any activity related to the sale of sexual products should be licensed and carried out only in specially designated areas. Such places, for example, cannot be placed near educational institutions, historical and cultural monuments, churches, mosques, and military units. Banning the sale of pornographic products in residential buildings, government offices, street stalls, markets, kiosks, and public transport is certainly a sign of the correct approach to the problem.

Regarding the question of the influence of erotic photos or scenes of sexual life on minors, the age of the participant and the comments and interpretations of the attractor (scammers) should be taken into account. The fact is that I.S. According to Kohn (1988), before puberty, children's motives for participating in sexual games and sex are far from erotic content and do not directly reflect the satisfaction of sexual desire [1].

We define (define) the main concepts within the topic under discussion. *Sex* [lat. *sexus*] is a set of mental reactions, concerns, attitude (setting) and actions related to sexual relationships, manifestation and satisfaction of sexual desire.

Erotica [from Greek *eroticos* - related to love] - sensuality, focus on sexual life, its depiction, a set of all things-events related to sexual love; psychological aspects specific to sexual life and its development; appearances in communication, fashion, art and more.

Pornography [Greek πόρνη – prostitute + γράφω – to write, depict] – to depict indecent scenes in a seductive way to arouse baser instincts; literature, painting or photography that serves this purpose, i.e. literature, visual arts, theater, cinema, etc., depict sexual life in a crude naturalistic, indecent manner.

Pornographic works, prints or other objects of a pornographic nature are obscene publications that depict the sexual life of people in an indecent manner and are intended to stimulate the sexual instincts in an unhealthy manner. It is allowed to engage in retail sales of mass media specializing in messages and materials of an erotic nature in closed transparent packaging and in specially designed rooms, the location of which is determined by the local administration.

One of the problems in the application of rules restricting the distribution of pornographic and similar information is the ambiguity of the difference between the concepts of "eroticism" and "pornography", since this issue is not defined in the regulatory documents, and even experts are not unanimous in this regard.

Sexologists have developed several criteria to distinguish erotica from pornography. In the interpretation of the famous sexologist I.S. Kohn, they are presented in the form of seven differences [2].

Firstly:

- erotic art depicts a person with all his feelings and experiences;
- pornography focuses a person's attention on certain aspects of sexual relations, that is, sex and the technique of its implementation.

Secondly:

- erotic art explores the human world;
- the function and purpose of pornography is one - to create or increase sexual arousal.

Thirdly:

- erotica is interested in all things unique and original;
- pornography is standard sex with minimal personal meaning.

Fourthly:

- erotic art builds its world according to the eternal laws of beauty;
- pornography reduces everything to the level of physiology, dehumanizes both man and erotica.

Fifthly:

- eroticism often reveals new depths of human existence that are not yet understood and not accepted by morality and public consciousness, violates the rules of etiquette.

Sixthly:

- eroticism is humane and moral, it expands the boundaries of human freedom;
- pornography denies morality by looking at a person like a microscope slide.

Seventhly:

- erotic art - a means of free creativity of the artist who creates unique works;
- pornography is a business that is part of the for-profit entertainment industry.

Pornography affects the psyche and behavior of people in different ways. For example, in one case, people who see such products emit certain impulses, they supposedly "ground" them, so their original behavior does not change at all. In other cases, such information is seen on the screen or acts as a motivation to perform similar actions towards others, or serves to recognize such behavior as a norm or even an ideal [3, 4].

F. Wortham, as a result of a clinical study of 200 teenagers, found that the display of violence, cruelty and sadism has a devastating effect on young people. He found out that they become hostile, cruel and insensitive to others, and concluded that in the process of socialization, their behavior becomes stronger.

Article 130 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the production, import, distribution, advertising, and display of pornographic products as a crime [5]. When investigating crimes in this area, special investigation is sometimes required. About 10 people - representatives of culture, art, Ministry of Justice, law enforcement agencies and educational institutions will be involved in its implementation. They express their opinion on a specific issue that arises in some criminal cases, based on their professional perception of erotica and pornography. Consequently, it is difficult to talk about any scientific evaluation of the products submitted for examination.

The lack of legal framework and qualified specialists in this field is creating certain problems in conducting expertise even now. Currently, the main criterion for determining the presence of pornographic elements is the representation of sex and male genitalia in a video product. In the case of printed products, even such criteria are not taken into account, and this situation has led to the appearance of a large number of pornographic products on the market. The Criminal Code only provides punishment for the illegal distribution of such products, and law enforcement officers are guided only by their own internal beliefs when assessing this.

As noted by V.F. Engalichev and S.S. Shipshin [6], complex forensic psychological and art science examination (CFPAS) is recommended in cases where it is necessary to determine the direction of the work of art and the degree of influence on the conscious or unconscious sphere of the person or the population as a whole. Practice shows that, in most cases, the complex commission invites for examination only objects whose content allows them to be included in real works of art only conditionally. These include magazines, books, brochures and videos with pornographic or sadistic content.

In particular, the following questions of a qualification nature are presented:

- 1) Are the files on the provided CD pornographic?
- 2) Are the video files on the provided CD related to pornographic material with images of minors?
- 3) Are the images on the CD pornographic, and if so, with what characters?
- 4) Are there signs (elements) of pornography in the presented videos?
- 5) Is this video material fiction or documentary? Do these images contain erotica or pornographic symbols in the videos?
- 6) Do the objects submitted for examination belong to pornographic or erotic products or not? If so, what are the symptoms?
- 7) Is there an image of a pornographic nature in the submitted photo?
- 8) Which files on the provided CD are pornographic?

We believe that the following list of expert diagnostic tasks is appropriate:

- 1) Is the information contained in the media presented for the study relevant to child pornography?
- 2) Did the person involved in the video recording perform or imitate sexual acts?
- 3) Does the video recording submitted for review include an image of a child's genitals for sexual purposes?

4) What are the consequences of the perception of the video recording presented to the expert from the point of view of the formation of sexual imagination and the development of morals in minors?

In order to answer the questions of interest to the court in criminal cases related to the production and distribution of pornographic materials, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive forensic examination, taking into account the tasks of qualification and diagnosis. It should be noted that the scope of the main issues described in the decision on the appointment of a comprehensive forensic expertise is determined by the examination of the special knowledge of experts necessary to determine the presence (or absence) of signs of pornography in the investigated objects, the tasks of investigating crimes.

Thus, it is recommended to ask the above-mentioned questions in front of a specialist-psychologist. Their responses reveal the patterns of sexually deviant behavior in the images presented in the study and the possible consequences for the consumer of viewing them. In order to formulate such questions, the examiner must clearly imagine what forms of sexual behavior correspond to the official signs of pornography. Accordingly, to identify the signs of pornography, the following questions can be asked to the complex expert:

1) Does viewing an image on a given object induce sexual desire? If so, what is the approximate form of its implementation: corrupt or natural (generally accepted, normal)?

2) Does viewing the image on the presented object lead to sexual aversion? If so, in terms of the consequences of watching it, does it lead to:

- a) development of deviant needs;
- b) change social relations in the direction of acceptability;
- c) formation of sexual anomalies;
- d) causes sexual disharmony and dysfunction;
- e) reduce sexual activity;
- f) disorder of psychosexual development.

In addition, the questions asked to the expert psychologist should take into account the spiritual direction of the image, visual focus, level of detail and the nature of influencing the psyche of the consumer.

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